

ANALYSIS OF A MOTORIZED JUICE EXTRACTOR USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY AND COST ANALYSIS

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Keywords: Analysis, RSM, Cost analysis, motorized juice extractor, fruit, blanching time, blanching temperature.

Abstract: Analysis of a motorized juice extractor using response surface methodology and cost analysis has been carried out. The study used RSM to analysis the effect of input variables on the responses which were the performance metrics. The cost of production of the machine was equally analyzed. The result of the work showed that for the range of variables considered in the performance analysis of the machine, maximum EE of 83.66% was obtained at the machine operating speed of 400 rpm, feed rate of 1.5 kg/min, blanching temperature of 80oC and blanching time of 6 min, while the maximum EC of 3.89 L/min was obtained at the machine operating speed of 500 rpm, feed rate of 1.0 kg/min, blanching temperature of 60oC and blanching time of 9 min. It was observed that an increase in operating speed and feed rate leads to increase in extraction efficiency after which there was a corresponding decrease in extraction efficiency at higher speed. An increase in the machine operating speed with blanching temperature leads to increase in extraction efficiency, after which there was a decline. An increase in operating speed with fruit blanching time resulted in an increase in the juice extraction efficiency and then a decrease in extraction efficiency. The results obtained for an increase in blanching temperature and feed rate, leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction efficiency. However, at higher temperatures and material feed rate, the extraction efficiency decreased. An increase in feed rate and blanching time leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction efficiency; however, at higher material feeding rate and blanching time, the extraction efficiency decreases. The result

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obtained showed that increase in operating speed and feed rate resulted in an increase in extraction capacity after which there was a corresponding decrease in extraction efficiency at higher speed. It is clear that the extraction capacity of the machine increased with increase in the machine operating speed and blanching temperature, after which there was a decline in extraction capacity. The range of variability between the actual and predicted extraction efficiency lies between 0.093 and -17.970. An increase in operating speed with fruit blanching time leads to an increase in the juice extraction capacity and then a decrease in extraction capacity. An increase in blanching temperature and feed rate leads to a corresponding increase in extraction capacity. However, at higher temperatures and material feed rate, the extraction machine capacity decreased. The result showed that an increase in feed rate with blanching time leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction capacity; however, at higher material feeding rate and blanching time, the extraction capacity decreases. An increase in fruit blanching time with blanching temperature leads to corresponding increase in the juice extraction capacity, and then extraction capacity decreases at higher temperature. The residual values in the table showed that the least residual value of 0.019 occurred at standard order of 15 and the highest residual value of -1.50 occurred at standard order of 13. The range of variability is 0.019 to -1.50 which is significant and the prediction model for juice extraction capacity has to be applied with some caution and physical observation of the juice extraction machine. Finally, the overall price for the produced machine is quite cheaper than the imported machine. The produced machine is ₦149800 (\$99.87) while the imported is ₦300000 (\$200).

1. INTRODUCTION

Fruit juice machines are used to extract the liquid portion of fruits from its solid portion and these machines are commonly called fruit juice extractors. The machines for extraction include presses, decanter centrifuge, pulper/finisher. There are several type of presses such as horizontal press, traditional rack and cloth press, belt press, hydraulic press, and screw press. In

selecting a juicer, the nature of the material to be processed should be taken into proper consideration.

In the work of Jackson (1988), an electrically powered juice pulping machine was fabricated with a lever operated press that grinds and crushes in one operation. An output of about 25 litres of juice per hour is obtained when the machine is operated by one person. The machine

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is a manually operated extractor with handle which aid in the production of juice free of seed and skin. The machine is fabricated with an auger-sieve combination mounted on top of an aluminium frame. The fruit press of the machine consists of a crusher mounted on top with components such as screw-thread, slated cage and a crusher.

In another study, Adewumi (1999) designed, developed and tested the performance of a 1.17 kW motorized fruit juice extractor operated at 1420 rpm for processing of citrus. The average juice extraction capacity of the fabricated machine for the tested orange and grape was found to be 5.11 and 2.79 kg/hr respectively while its extraction efficiency for the tested orange and grape was determined to be 78.78 and 75.66 % respectively. The extraction capacity of the fabricated juicer for orange juice extraction was found to be 280 % of the manual extraction method and 304 % of the value obtained using the domestic extraction cup. While for grape juice extraction, the machine extraction capacity was found to be 220 % of the manual extraction method and 180 % of the value obtained using the extraction cup. On modification of the machine and by replacing the tapered auger with a straight auger, the juice extraction efficiency of the machine increased from 78.9 to 89.2 % while the machine extraction capacity increased from 5.1 to 15.8 kg/h for the tested sweet orange. To evaluate the effect of fruit size (thickness) and shaft speeds with respect to machine extraction efficiency and capacity using regression analysis,

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fruits were reduced to uniform sizes with thickness of 20, 40, and 60 mm and shaft speeds of 300, 400, 500 and 600 rpm. The study showed very strong quadratic relationships between the machine extraction efficiency, machine capacity, and machine speed for the 3 sizes of pineapple and orange fruits studied. The exception was apple of 60 mm thickness which showed a very strong linear relationship between the shaft speed and machine capacity. The study also determined the relationships among various parameters while and the optimum speeds for peak performance of the machine at various fruit thicknesses were also recommended by the author.

A study by Badmus and Adeyemi (2004) designed, fabricated and evaluated the performance of a small scale whole fruit juice extractor for processing of pineapples. By performance, the study showed that the fabricated juicer was able to convert about 12 kg of ripe pineapple fruit into 8 L of pineapple juice. The juicer was fabricated with beater blades, a shaft with a powered screw pressing mechanism. To evaluate the extraction performance of a mechanized fruit juicer as a function of its extraction efficiency, Ishiwu and Oluka (2004) designed and developed a fruit juice extractor which consists of a screw jack, frame, connecting screw rod, pressing mechanism, interlock, feeding pot, receiving pot and discharge mechanism. The results showed a juice yield of about 76 % with machine extraction efficiency and extraction loss of 83 % and 3 % respectively.

The work of Kailappan *et al.* (2005) fabricated and tested a tomato seed extractor having a capacity of about 180 kg of fruits/h. The study showed that the fabricated machine, with a unit cost of \$190, has a seed extraction efficiency of 98.8 % with saving time and saving cost of 96.6 and 89.6 % respectively when compared with the manual method of seed extraction. To evaluate the maximum juice yield of grape, water melon and pine apple, tangerine, orange, Oyeleke and Olaniyan (2007) examined the performance of a small-scale motorized multi-juice extractor fabricated in India. The extraction efficiency of the tested machine was found to be 81.3 %. Kasozi and Kasisira (2005) designed and fabricated a banana juicer which operates on the principle of impact and friction due to the action of a mixer on the banana and rough wall of the extraction chamber. The study showed that a juice extraction efficiency of 47 % was obtained. Nidhi and Matthew (2006) developed guava candies by modifying the normal procedure for preparing confectionary items. Report showed that the candies prepared can be safely stored for 2 and 4 months under ambient and refrigerated conditions, respectively.

Olaniyan (2010) designed and developed a 2 hp motorized small scale orange juice extractor having a capacity of 14 kg/h with a machine cost of about \$100 using locally available materials. The fabricated machine consists of a main frame, feeding hopper, transmission belt, top cover, juice collector, worm shaft, juice sieve, waste outlet, pulleys and bearings. The worm shaft

does the conveying, crushing, pressing and squeezing of the fruit to extract the required juice. The extracted juice is then filtered through the sieve into the collector while the residual waste is discharged through the waste outlet. The study showed an average juice yield of 41.6 % and extraction efficiency of about 57.4 %.

To develop a juicer which is affordable, environmentally friendly, energy efficient and versatile in the processing of fruits, Adewumi and Ukwenya (2012) designed and produced a motorized juice extractor for the juice and pulp of a mango fruit. The developed machine consisted of a main frame, hopper, auger, extraction unit, shaft, juice outlet, belt and pulley, bearing, top cover and the machine frame. The auger shaft is designed with a diameter of 18 mm while the auger has a pitch of 8.8 cm. The juicer is fabricated with a 1.42 hp electric motor, and the machine cost is less than fifty thousand Naira (₦33,33). Juice extraction efficiency, juice extraction capacity and thorough-put of the machine were determined at various speeds of 300, 600 and 900 rpm. For shaft speed of 300 rpm, the machine extraction efficiency was found to be 76 % while the machine extraction capacity of 26.67 Lh⁻¹ was recorded at shaft speed of 900 rpm. Also, maximum thorough-put value of 14.36 g/s was determined and recorded at shaft speed of 900 rpm. The study established linear relationships between shaft speed and juice extraction efficiency, juice extraction capacity and thorough-put of the machine.

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Sylvester and Abugh (2012) designed and fabricated a manually operated orange juice extractor having a diameter of 160 mm and a height of 350 mm. The juice is extracted by a rotational motion of small sharpened blades mounted on a shaft. The rotation is achieved by turning the handle. The machine is fabricated with two main parts – a goblet and a manually operated mechanical unit. The manually operated mechanical unit consists of a pair of bevel gear casings, two bearings and two shafts. It has a handle welded to the horizontal shaft. Small sharpened blades were produced and then mounted onto the impeller shaft with a bearing fixed underneath and a shaft passed through. To prevent leakage, a dynamic seal is used to separate the shaft, bearing. The performance analysis of the machine showed that the fabricated juicer was able to process between 180 - 220 oranges per hour into orange juice.

Food preservation plays an essential role in the conservation and better utilization of fruits and vegetables in order to prevent the glut while utilizing the surplus during offseason. It becomes very important to employ adequate processing methods to preserve them for utilization during offseason and also use modern techniques or methods to extend their shelf life for better distribution (Vidhya and Narain, 2011). Fruits are better preserved by processing it into products such as jam, jelly, fruit bar, juice, pickle and murabba as this helps to extend their utilizable lifespan. Fruit juicing is the easiest and

most important method of preserving fruits for utilization during offseason.

The production of juices made from fruits and vegetables is very important both from the human health and commercial standpoints. The availability of nutritious elements from fruits and vegetables to both domestic and industrial users of fruits is thus facilitated by the marketing of fruits juices. To meet local commercial needs, the processing of fruit and vegetable juice requires adequate methods for extraction, clarification and stabilization (Bhat, 2000).

Juicing is an extraction process by which the liquid portion of the fruit is efficiently separated from its solid portion by means of a juicer. The quality of the juice produced will depend on the variety and maturity of the processed fresh fruit (Oyeleke and Olaniyan, 2007). Extraction of juice is preceded by hot, cold and enzymatic treatments (Singh, Kumar and Sharma, 2012).

The extraction of fruit juice involves several steps which includes crushing, squeezing and pressing of whole fruit in order to obtain the juice and reduce the bulkiness of the fruit to liquid and pulp. According to Bhatia (1989) and Abulude *et al* (2007), the various processes in fruit processing process include sorting, washing, pressing, slicing, crushing and extraction, addition of additives, homogenization, pasteurization (heat treatment), packaging and storage and this process is represented in Figure 1.1.

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Figure 1.1: Fruit juice processing process

Source: Abulude *et al.*, (2007)

In this present work the objective of the research is to analysis a newly developed motorized juice extractor using response surface methodology and cost analysis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this work include the bill of quantity for the production of the motorized juice extractor, data generated during the testing

of the machine, computer, and computer software.

2.1.1 Description of the fruit Juice Extractor

The juice extractor was designed to work on the principle of compression and squeezing due to the gradual reduction of clearance between conveyor housing and screw conveyor. It is made up of five units, namely main frame, feed hopper, juice extraction unit, collecting unit, and power and transmission unit (Figure 2.1).

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.1: (a) Photograph and, (b) 3D photo-rendering of the fruit juice Extraction Machine

2.1.2 Performance Test of the Machine

Performance testing and evolution were performed on the fabricated motorized fruit juice extraction machine at completion of the

construction. The tests were carried out at the designed operation speed of 525.23 rpm. However, the tests were carried out so as to determine the following:

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- i. The rate of extraction and capacity of machine.
- ii. Possible leakage in the fabricated machine.
- iii. Hours or minute per hour the machine can operate.
- iv. The percentage and the efficiency of the machine.
- v. Number of hours, the operator or engineer can operate on it, in order to know the accurate time to dismantle the conveyor or conical restriction section.

The machine performance test was carried out by pouring a known mass of orange fruit into the hopper. The power source was switch on to run the electric motor, which in turn powers the machine. The orange fruit in the hopper were then delivered in to the extraction chamber and the machine was allowed to operate until the material was completely fed and extracted. After that, mass of fruit fed into the machine, mass of juice extracted, mass of residual waste and juice constant of the fruit in decimal were recorded. The juice constant was obtained from the ratio of sum of masses of juice extracted and juice in chaff to the mass of fruit fed in. The mass of juice in chaff was determined using the method of ASAE (1983) as applied by Aviara *et al.* (2008), and Oje (1993). This involved oven drying the chaff at 130°C until a constant weight was reached. Each experiment was replicated three times for the peeled oranges.

The performance evaluation of the juice extractor was carried out on the basis of the

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following indices used by Tressler and Joslyn (1961):

$$\text{Juice yield, } J_y = \frac{100 \times W_{JE}}{W_{JE} + W_{RW}} \% \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Extraction Efficiency, } EE = \frac{100 \times W_{JE}}{xW_{FS}} \% \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Extraction loss, } El \% = \frac{100 [W_{FS} - (W_{JE} + W_{RW})]}{W_{FS}} \% \quad (3)$$

Where W_{RW} = Residual waste/dry chaff (kg), EE = Extraction Efficiency, %; W_{JE} = mass of juice extracted, g ; W_{FS} = mass of feed sample, g ; x = juice constant of fruit, *decimal*

$$\text{Extraction Capacity, } EC = \frac{V_j}{T} \quad (4)$$

Where EC = Extraction Capacity, $L/min.$; V_j = volume of juice extracted from fruit material, *litre*; T = juice extraction time, *min.*

2.1.3 Response Surface Methodology (RSM)

A Design Expert (version 6.0.6) software package for design of experiments was adopted on order to analyze and generate model equations for the expression process. The data which was obtained through the experimental matrix was computed for the determination of regression coefficient of the second order multiple regression models. The analysis of regression and variance was performed by the Design Expert. In order to validate the optimal parameters, the experiment was repeated at the optimal conditions as suggested by Islau *et al.*,

(2002). Thus, the obtained results were compared with predicted values.

2.1.4 Cost Analysis of the Motorized Fruit Juice Extraction Machine

The cost of the construction materials and other components of the juice extraction machine is presented in Table 3.4. A feasibility study was carried out based on the engineering materials selected for the construction of the machine. The total cost of the juice extraction machine is estimated to be ₦149,800. The various parts are easily affordable in case of failure of any part of the machine. The maintenance of the developed juice extraction system is easy and parts are readily available.

Table 3.1: Juice extraction efficiency and Extraction capacity at different processing Condition combinations

Run	OS (rpm)	FR (kg/min)	BT (°C)	Bt (min)	JEE (%)	JEC (L/min)
1	400.00	1.50	40.00	0.00	41.60	0.28
2	300.00	1.00	20.00	3.00	31.63	1.25
3	500.00	1.00	20.00	3.00	55.31	1.82
4	300.00	2.00	20.00	3.00	46.00	0.97
5	500.00	2.00	20.00	3.00	72.37	3.55
6	300.00	1.00	60.00	3.00	41.31	0.08
7	500.00	1.00	60.00	3.00	57.71	1.55
8	300.00	2.00	60.00	3.00	53.94	1.07
9	500.00	2.00	60.00	3.00	74.74	3.11
10	400.00	1.50	0.00	6.00	40.66	0.95
11	400.00	0.50	40.00	6.00	49.89	0.76
12	200.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	39.09	0.26
13	400.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	69.54	2.58
14	400.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	68.83	2.73
15	400.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	68.80	2.63

The results and discussion of the research work is presented under results and discussion below in the next section.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

3.1.1 Juice Extraction Machine Performance Analysis

Table 3.1 depicts the average summary of the juice extraction efficiency and juice extraction capacity at various extraction process condition combinations using 4 factors, 5 levels, factorial Central Composite Rotatable Design (CCRD) of Response Surface Methodology (RSM).

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16	400.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	69.14	3.83
17	400.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	69.26	3.48
18	400.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	69.43	3.26
19	600.00	1.50	40.00	6.00	49.34	1.42
20	400.00	2.50	40.00	6.00	58.11	2.24
21	400.00	1.50	80.00	6.00	83.66	2.53
22	300.00	1.00	20.00	9.00	46.63	1.21
23	500.00	1.00	20.00	9.00	66.46	3.00
24	300.00	2.00	20.00	9.00	48.57	1.13
25	500.00	2.00	20.00	9.00	79.40	3.67
26	300.00	1.00	60.00	9.00	49.14	1.52
27	500.00	1.00	60.00	9.00	70.14	3.89
28	300.00	2.00	60.00	9.00	59.09	2.52
29	500.00	2.00	60.00	9.00	52.09	3.40
30	400.00	1.50	40.00	12.00	67.60	2.02

3.1.2 Juice Extraction Efficiency

Figures (3.1 - 3.6) shows the effects of juice extraction factors on the juice extraction efficiency, while Table 3.2 depicts the diagnostics case statistics for juice extraction efficiency. The table shows the predicted values of juice extraction efficiency using the developed quadratic regression model.

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Figure 3.1: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of feed rate and operating speed on juice extraction efficiency

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Figure 3.2: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching temperature and operating speed on juice extraction efficiency

Figure 3.3: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching time and operating speed on juice extraction efficiency

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Figure 3.4: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching temperature and feed rate on juice extraction efficiency

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Figure 3.5: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching time and feed rate on juice extraction efficiency

Figure 3.6: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching time and blanching temperature on juice extraction efficiency

Table 3.2: Diagnostics Case Statistics for juice extraction efficiency (%)

Standar Order	Actua l Value	Predicte d Value	Residua l	Leverag e	Student Residua l	Cook's Distanc e	Outlie r t	Run Orde r
1	59.09	57.82	1.270	0.583	0.223	0.005	0.216	28
2	69.26	69.17	0.093	0.167	0.012	0.000	0.011	17
3	40.66	48.78	-8.120	0.583	-1.422	0.189	-1.477	10
4	39.09	35.14	3.950	0.583	0.692	0.045	0.679	12
5	53.94	49.83	4.110	0.583	0.719	0.048	0.707	8
6	46.63	47.96	-1.330	0.583	-0.232	0.005	-0.225	22
7	41.31	41.48	-0.170	0.583	-0.029	0.000	-0.028	6
8	70.14	66.03	4.110	0.583	0.720	0.048	0.708	27
9	57.71	50.12	7.590	0.583	1.330	0.165	1.368	7
10	42.60	39.42	3.180	0.583	0.557	0.029	0.544	2

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11	58.11	69.75	-11.640	0.583	-2.039	0.388	-2.317	20
12	67.60	67.88	-0.280	0.583	-0.049	0.000	-0.047	30
13	49.34	67.31	-17.970	0.583	-3.147	0.924	*	19
14	69.14	69.17	-0.027	0.167	-0.003	0.000	-0.003	16
15	48.57	48.92	-0.350	0.583	-0.062	0.000	-0.060	24
16	66.46	63.33	3.130	0.583	0.549	0.028	0.536	23
17	49.14	52.40	-3.260	0.583	-0.571	0.030	-0.558	26
18	79.40	72.45	6.950	0.583	1.217	0.138	1.238	25
19	68.83	69.17	-0.340	0.167	-0.042	0.000	-0.040	14
20	69.54	69.17	0.370	0.167	0.046	0.000	0.045	13
21	83.66	79.60	4.060	0.583	0.711	0.047	0.698	29
22	74.74	66.63	8.110	0.583	1.420	0.188	1.475	9
23	55.31	49.80	5.510	0.583	0.965	0.087	0.963	3
24	49.89	52.27	-2.380	0.583	-0.416	0.016	-0.405	11
25	72.37	61.87	10.500	0.583	1.839	0.316	2.019	5
26	46.00	43.33	2.670	0.583	0.468	0.020	0.455	4
27	32.63	46.37	-13.740	0.583	-2.407	0.541	-2.968	1
28	52.09	57.99	-5.900	0.583	-1.033	0.100	-1.036	21
29	68.80	69.17	-0.370	0.167	-0.045	0.000	-0.044	15
30	69.43	69.17	0.260	0.167	0.033	0.000	0.032	18

* Case(s) with |Outlier T| > 3.50

3.1.3 Juice Extraction Capacity

Figures (3.7 - 3.12) shows the effects of juice extraction process conditions on the juice extraction capacity and Table 3.3: depicts

diagnostics case statistics for juice extraction capacity. The table shows the predicted values juice extraction capacity compared with actual experimental values.

Figure 3.7: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of feed rate and operating speed on juice extraction capacity

Figure 3.8: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching temperature and operating speed on juice extraction capacity

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Figure 3.9: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching time and operating speed on juice extraction capacity

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Figure 3.10: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching temperature and Feed rate on juice extraction capacity

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Figure 3.11: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching time and feed rat on juice extraction capacity

Figure 3.12: Response surface plot of the interactive effects of blanching time and blanching temperature on juice extraction capacity

Table 3.3: Diagnostics Case Statistics for juice extraction capacity (L/min)

Standard Order	Actual Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Leverage	Student Residual	Cook's Distance	Outlier	Run Order
1	2.52	2.27	0.250	0.583	0.489	0.022	0.477	28
2	3.48	3.09	0.390	0.167	0.551	0.004	0.538	17
3	0.95	1.97	-1.020	0.583	-2.003	0.375	-2.261	10
4	0.76	0.33	0.430	0.583	0.855	0.068	0.847	12
5	1.07	1.25	-0.180	0.583	-0.348	0.011	-0.337	8
6	1.21	1.12	0.091	0.583	0.180	0.003	0.174	22
7	0.08	0.27	-0.190	0.583	-0.382	0.014	-0.371	6
8	3.40	2.75	0.650	0.583	1.285	0.154	1.316	27
9	1.55	1.01	0.540	0.583	1.060	0.105	1.065	7
10	1.25	0.64	0.610	0.583	1.208	0.136	1.228	2

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11	2.24	2.62	-0.380	0.583	-0.757	0.053	-0.745	20
12	2.02	2.55	-0.530	0.583	-1.049	0.103	-1.053	30
13	1.42	2.92	-1.500	0.583	-2.960	0.818	*	19
14	3.83	3.09	0.740	0.167	1.040	0.014	1.043	16
15	1.13	1.11	0.019	0.583	0.037	0.000	0.036	24
16	3.00	2.27	0.730	0.583	1.445	0.195	1.505	23
17	1.52	1.78	-0.260	0.583	-0.512	0.024	-0.499	26
18	3.67	2.97	0.700	0.583	1.391	0.180	1.439	25
19	2.73	3.09	-0.360	0.167	-0.495	0.003	-0.483	14
20	2.58	3.09	-0.510	0.167	-0.705	0.007	-0.692	13
21	3.89	3.95	-0.056	0.583	-0.111	0.001	-0.107	29
22	3.11	2.69	0.420	0.583	0.828	0.064	0.819	9
23	1.82	1.56	0.260	0.583	0.519	0.025	0.506	3
24	0.27	0.95	-0.680	0.583	-1.349	0.170	-1.390	11
25	3.55	2.73	0.820	0.583	1.609	0.242	1.709	5
26	0.97	1.11	-0.140	0.583	-0.277	0.007	-0.268	4
27	0.28	0.82	-0.540	0.583	-1.056	0.104	-1.060	1
28	2.53	2.58	-0.052	0.583	-0.102	0.001	-0.099	21
29	2.63	3.09	-0.460	0.167	-0.635	0.005	-0.622	15
30	3.26	3.09	0.170	0.167	0.244	0.001	0.236	18

* Case(s) with $|\text{Outlier T}| > 3.50$

3.1.4 Cost Analysis

Table 3.4 shows the breakdown of the cost incurred in producing the newly developed motorized juice extractor

Table 3.4: Bill of Engineering Measurements and Evaluations (BEME) of the Juice Extraction Machine

S/N	Description	Size	Qty.	Unit Price (₦) (\$)	Total (₦) (\$)
1	Stainless steel Shaft	20 x 2100 mm	1	7,500 (5)	7,500 (5)
2	Stainless steel sheet (gauge-8, 4.18 mm)	609.6 x 609.6 mm	1	28,000 (18.7)	28,000 (18.7)
3	1-inch mild steel angle bar	5486.4 mm	1	1,800 (1.2)	1,800 (1.2)

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4	Flange bearing	6204	2	2,200 (1.5)	4,400 (2.93)
5	Variable geared Electric motor (3-phase)	2 hp	1	50,000 (33.3)	50,000(33.3)
6	Pulley	60 and 100 mm	2	1,000 (0.67)	2,000 (1.3)
7	Gear tooth		2	2,000 (1.3)	4,000 (2.67)
8	Bolts & Nuts	M8, M10, M12, M14			2,200 (1.5)
9	Panting & accessories				5,500 (3.67)
10	Labour				30,000 (20)
11	Miscellaneous				15,000 (10)
Total					149,800 (99.87)

3.2 Discussion

Table 3.1 shows result for the juice extraction efficiency and capacity at various levels combination of operating speed, feed rate, blanching temperature and blanching time. For the range of extraction process conditions considered in the expression process of juice from orange, the highest juice extraction efficiency of 83.66% was obtained at the machine operating speed of 400 rpm, feed rate of 1.5 kg/min, blanching temperature of 80°C and blanching time of 6 min, while the lowest juice extraction efficiency of 31.63% was obtained at the machine operating speed of 300 rpm, feed rate of 1.0 kg/min, blanching temperature of

20°C and blanching time of 3 min as shown in Table 3.1. Also, the highest extraction capacity of 3.89 L/min was obtained at the machine operating speed of 500 rpm, feed rate of 1.0 kg/min, blanching temperature of 60°C and blanching time of 9 min, while the lowest extraction capacity of 0.26 L/min was obtained at the machine operating speed of 200 rpm, feed rate of 1.5 kg/min, blanching temperature of 40°C and blanching time of 6 min as shown in Table 3.1. The juice extraction efficiency ranges from 31.63 to 83.66% while the juice extraction efficiency ranges from 0.26 to 3.89 L/min (Table 3.1). This compares favourably with the maximum juice extraction efficiencies of other

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developed machines for fruits (Oje, (1993); Aviara *et al.* (2008); Bawa, 2025).

In Figure 3.1, it was observed that an increase in operating speed and feed rate leads to increase in extraction efficiency after which there was a corresponding decrease in extraction efficiency at higher speed.

As presented in Figure 3.2, an increase in the machine operating speed with blanching temperature leads to increase in extraction efficiency, after which there was a decline. At high temperature, protein coagulation, increase in the liquid fluidity, liquid-cells breakdown and moisture content adjustment to the optimum level were achieved faster. This was in agreement with the findings of Oje (1993), Oyeleke and Olaniyan (2007), Aviara *et al.*, (2008), Olaniyan (2010), Adebayo *et al.*, (2014), Olaniyan and Obajemihi (2014).

From Figure 3.3, an increase in operating speed with fruit blanching time resulted in an increase in the juice extraction efficiency and then a decrease in extraction efficiency. At lower temperature levels, evaporation causes the surface of the sample to harden, thus requiring a higher pressure or speed to overcome the hardened sample during extraction. This agrees with the findings of other researchers (Oje (1993); Aviara *et al.* (2008); Bawa, 2025).

The results obtained for an increase in blanching temperature and feed rate as presented in Figure 3.4, leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction efficiency. However, at higher temperatures and material feed rate, the

extraction efficiency decreased. At higher blanching temperatures, protein coagulation and viscosity reduction take place at a faster rate leading to increase in the fluid flow at less feeding rate durations; while extending the increasing the feeding rate at higher blanching temperatures caused substantial moisture loss leading to hardening of samples which consequently leads to a decrease in extraction efficiency (Bawa, 2025).

As depicted in Figure 3.5, an increase in feed rate and blanching time leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction efficiency; however, at higher material feeding rate and blanching time, the extraction efficiency decreases. Heating the samples makes the mesocarp soft with a consequent reduction in the fluid viscosity. The softening of tissues weakens the cellular structure, making it highly liable to failure under applied pressures. However, according to Bargale *et al.*, (1999), temperature decreases the viscosity of the juice thereby increasing its fluidity through the compressed medium, whereas an increase in pressure makes the fibre harder which restricts the flow of the liquid.

In Figure 3.6, an increase in fruit blanching time with blanching temperature leads to corresponding increase in the juice extraction efficiency, and then extraction efficiency decreases at higher temperature. Heating the samples at prolonged times makes the fruit brittle with a consequent reduction in liquid viscosity. The softening of fruit cells weakens the

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cellular structure, making it highly liable to failure under pressure.

The result obtained in Figure 3.7 showed that increase in operating speed and feed rate resulted in an increase in extraction capacity after which there was a corresponding decrease in extraction efficiency at higher speed. From Figure 3.8, it is clear that the extraction capacity of the machine increased with increase in the machine operating speed and blanching temperature, after which there was a decline in extraction capacity. This was in agreement with the findings of Aviara *et al.*, (2008), Olaniyan (2010).

Table 3.2 is the diagnostic case statistics for juice extraction % efficiency. The presented juice extraction efficiency actual values, which were derived from experimental design are compared with model derived values from the best model. The residual values in the table are low in some standard order, while very high in others. Standard order 13 show a residual value of -17.970 which means the predicted value is more than the actual value by 17. Standard order 2 shows that the residual value is 0.093 which means the predicted value is less than the actual value by 0.093 which is quite insignificant. The range of variability between the actual and predicted extraction efficiency lies between 0.093 and -17.970. This indicates that the prediction model for the juice extraction efficiency has to be used with caution (Bawa, 2025).

Figure 3.9 showed that an increase in operating speed with fruit blanching time leads to an increase in the juice extraction capacity and then a decrease in extraction capacity. At lower temperature levels, evaporation causes the surface of the sample to harden, thus requiring a higher pressure or speed to overcome the hardened sample during extraction.

In Figure 3.10, an increase in blanching temperature and feed rate leads to a corresponding increase in extraction capacity. However, at higher temperatures and material feed rate, the extraction machine capacity decreased. At higher blanching temperatures, protein coagulation and viscosity reduction take place at a faster rate leading to increase in the fluid flow at less feeding rate durations; while extending the increasing the feeding rate at higher blanching temperatures caused substantial moisture loss leading to hardening of samples which consequently leads to a decrease in extraction capacity (Bawa, 2025).

The result in Figure 3.11 showed that an increase in feed rate with blanching time leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction capacity; however, at higher material feeding rate and blanching time, the extraction capacity decreases. Heating the samples makes the mesocarp soft with a consequent reduction in the fluid viscosity. The softening of tissues weakens the cellular structure, making it highly liable to failure under applied pressures. However, according to Bargale *et al.*, (1999), temperature decreases the viscosity of the juice thereby

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increasing its fluidity through the compressed medium, whereas an increase in pressure makes the fibre harder which restricts the flow of the liquid. This agrees with the findings of other researchers (Adewumi (1999); Badmus and Adeyemi (2004); Kailappan *et al.* (2005)).

In Figure 3.12, an increase in fruit blanching time with blanching temperature leads to corresponding increase in the juice extraction capacity, and then extraction capacity decreases at higher temperature. Heating the samples at prolonged times makes the fruit brittle with a consequent reduction in liquid viscosity (Kailappan *et al.* 2005; Bawa, 2025).

Table 3.3 is the diagnostic case statistics for juice extraction capacity. The table presented juice extraction capacity actual values compared with model predicted values for juice extraction capacity. The residual values in the table showed that the least residual value of 0.019 occurred at standard order of 15 and the highest residual value of -1.50 occurred at standard order of 13. The range of variability is 0.019 to -1.50 which is significant and the prediction model for juice extraction capacity has to be applied with some caution and physical observation of the juice extraction machine (Badmus and Adeyemi 2006).

Table 3.4 is the bill of engineering measurements and evaluation (BEME) of the newly developed juice extraction machine. The table shows that the prices were quite reasonable and the overall price for the produced machine is quite cheaper than the imported machine. The produced

machine is ₦149800 (\$99.87) while the imported is ₦300000 (\$200).

4. CONCLUSION

Analysis of a motorized juice extractor using response surface methodology and cost analysis has been carried out. The study has drawn the following conclusions:

1. For the range of variables considered in the performance analysis of the machine, maximum EE of 83.66% was obtained at the machine operating speed of 400 rpm, feed rate of 1.5 kg/min, blanching temperature of 80°C and blanching time of 6 min, while the maximum EC of 3.89 L/min was obtained at the machine operating speed of 500 rpm, feed rate of 1.0 kg/min, blanching temperature of 60°C and blanching time of 9 min.
2. It was observed that an increase in operating speed and feed rate leads to increase in extraction efficiency after which there was a corresponding decrease in extraction efficiency at higher speed.
3. An increase in the machine operating speed with blanching temperature leads to increase in extraction efficiency, after which there was a decline.
4. An increase in operating speed with fruit blanching time resulted in an increase in the juice extraction efficiency and then a decrease in extraction efficiency
5. The results obtained for an increase in blanching temperature and feed rate, leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction efficiency. However, at higher temperatures and

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material feed rate, the extraction efficiency decreased.

6. An increase in feed rate and blanching time leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction efficiency; however, at higher material feeding rate and blanching time, the extraction efficiency decreases.

7. The result obtained showed that increase in operating speed and feed rate resulted in an increase in extraction capacity after which there was a corresponding decrease in extraction efficiency at higher speed. It is clear that the extraction capacity of the machine increased with increase in the machine operating speed and blanching temperature, after which there was a decline in extraction capacity

8. The range of variability between the actual and predicted extraction efficiency lies between 0.093 and -17.970.

9. An increase in operating speed with fruit blanching time leads to an increase in the juice extraction capacity and then a decrease in extraction capacity.

10. An increase in blanching temperature and feed rate leads to a corresponding increase in extraction capacity. However, at higher

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temperatures and material feed rate, the extraction machine capacity decreased.

11. The result showed that an increase in feed rate with blanching time leads to a corresponding increase in juice extraction capacity; however, at higher material feeding rate and blanching time, the extraction capacity decreases.

12. An increase in fruit blanching time with blanching temperature leads to corresponding increase in the juice extraction capacity, and then extraction capacity decreases at higher temperature.

13. The residual values in the table showed that the least residual value of 0.019 occurred at standard order of 15 and the highest residual value of -1.50 occurred at standard order of 13. The range of variability is 0.019 to -1.50 which is significant and the prediction model for juice extraction capacity has to be applied with some caution and physical observation of the juice extraction machine.

14. Finally, the overall price for the produced machine is quite cheaper than the imported machine. The produced machine is ₦149800 (\$99.87) while the imported is ₦300000 (\$200).

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